

New concepts in development of nuclear energy (Small modular reactors with lead containing coolant)

Sonia M. Hammachi¹, Plamen V. Petkov*²

¹ International School UWEKIND 48, Vladayska str. 1606 Sofia Center, Sofia

² Sofia University "St. Kliment Ohridski," 1164 Sofia, Bulgaria 5 James Bouchier Blvd, Faculty of Physics

Abstract:

The poster presents a general characterization of GEN IV small modular reactors where their advantages over the traditional nuclear energy production are pointed out. The concept STAR –Secure Transportable Autonomous Reactor is also introduced there. A summary of the following existing projects is to be presented: SSTAR of 20 MWe (USA), BREST-300 (Russia), Europe's 300 MWt ALFRED and Belgium's MYRRHA. The Westinghouse company also announced that they had submitted a proposal for a Liquid Metal Fast Reactor (LFR) project development. The focus of the poster is on the overall design of existing projects. The scope of existing projects' applicability is also discussed.

Scheme of two types of convection in SMR

Small modular reactors (SMRs): Advanced nuclear reactors with a power capacity of up to 300 MW(e) per unit, which is about one-third of the generating capacity of traditional nuclear power reactors.

Parameter	BREST	SSTAR	ALFRED	MYRRHA	LFR
Coolant type	lead	lead	lead	lead-bismuth	lead
Core lifetime	refueled	15-20 years	refueled	refueled	refueled
Power, MWe	300	19.8	125	20-30	460
Convection	forced	natural	forced	forced	forced
Efficiency	40%	44%	41%	---	42%
Secondary fluid	water/steam	CO ₂	water/steam	water/steam	CO ₂
Cycle	Rankine	Brayton	Rankine	Rankine	Brayton
ADS	none	none	none	yes	none

Conclusions:

- The presented nuclear reactors are of type **small modular reactors** (except Westinghouse LFR, which is considered medium sized) and all of them are **lead cooled fast reactors** as this is the **most effective technology for future GEN IV**.
- In order to **compare their effectiveness** we developed a parameter that we called **Productivity**. It shows that the **most effective is BREST** and the **least effective is MYRRHA**.

Westinghouse LFR

Has a closed fuel cycle for efficient conversion of fertile uranium. It can also be used as a burner of MAs (Minor Actinides) from spent fuel and as a burner/breeder. The plan for **commercial operation is within the next five years**. The lead coolant is contained inside a reactor vessel surrounded by a guard vessel. **Pb is a coolant with very low neutron absorption and moderation**, making it possible to **maintain a fast neutron flux** even with a large amount of coolant in the core. The use of Pb means a **simpler design and lower capital costs**. There are, however, some disadvantages to using Pb related to that the experience using Pb coolant is limited.

MYRRHA

Modular and flexible irradiation facilities, based on the **Accelerator Driven Systems (ADS)** concept, which are subcritical systems where the **deficit on the neutron balance is counterbalanced with externally produced neutrons**. These neutrons arise during the process of spallation when a proton beam, produced by an accelerator, is fired into a spallation target. **The conditions reached in an ADS allow the transmutation of long-lived nuclear waste in short-lived waste, reducing the time scale of final disposal**.* At about 350 MeV, an incident proton delivers 7 MeV kinetic energy per spallation neutron. Almost 85% of the incident energy exits the target in the form of "evaporation" energy of the nuclei.

*The idea was first proposed by Nobel prize laureate E.O. Lawrence in the 1950's and revived by another Nobel prize laureate C. Rubbia in 1993 after recent major advances in accelerator technology.

Generation IV requirements

Sustainability: (1) sustainable energy generation meeting clean air objectives, promoting long-term availability of systems and effective fuel utilization; (2) minimize and manage nuclear waste and notably reduce the long-term stewardship burden.

Economics: (1) clear life-cycle cost advantage over other energy sources; (2) comparable level of financial risk to other energy projects.

Safety and Reliability: (1) excel in safety and reliability; (2) very low likelihood and degree of reactor core damage; (3) eliminate the need for off site emergency response.

Proliferation Resistance and Physical Protection: (1) provide increased physical protection against acts of terrorism and nuclear materials theft.

BREST-300

It is **dual-cycle cooling**, steam generating power unit, comprising reactor itself with steam generators, pumps, refueling equipment, control and protection system, concrete well with thermal insulation, steam turbine plant, heat removal system being used in reactor cooldown, reactor heat up system, reactor overpressure protection system, primary coolant cleanup system, gas cleanup system and other subsidiary systems. The construction of the BREST-300-OD in Seversk (near Tomsk) was approved and began on 8 June, 2021. **Commercial operation is planned to begin in 2029**.

SSTAR

Reactor design for countries with developing economies and infrastructures, or to sites with remote locations requiring standalone power supply. It is based on the concept of a small transportable autonomous reactor (STAR) intended for use in remote locations with these features:

- (1) a reactor core designed for no refueling or whole-core replacement;
- (2) **transportability: delivered assembled**;
- (3) **the core is designed for 15–30 year core life**;
- (4) **the capability for autonomous load following**;
- (5) **remote monitoring for operational occurrences**.

Key characteristics: coolant circulation by **natural convection** where for all regimes no reactor coolant pumps are considered; a supercritical CO₂ power conversion system providing for improved efficiency by **Brayton cycle**; sealed vessel designed for **complete replacement when refueling is required**.

ALFRED

A small-size reactor where the primary components are contained in the main reactor vessel, located in a large pool within the reactor tank. The coolant flow coming from the cold pool enters the core and once passed through the latter, is collected in a volume to be distributed to eight parallel pipes and delivered to as many SGs. After leaving the coolant enters the cold pool and returns to the core. The core is composed of **171 wrapped hexagonal Fuel Assemblies (FAs)**. **Two different and independent control rod systems** ensure reactivity swing control and safe shut-down. The **working fluid is water**, which in SG exchanges heat with lead, evaporates and overheats until it goes to the steam header from which it is conveyed in the steamline towards the turbine.